

Cities and urban areas are central to global decarbonization pathways

Diego Manyá^{1*}, Mark Roelfsema^{2,3}, Yuetong Zhang¹, Ying Yu⁴, Gunner Luderer^{5,6}, Pascal Weigmann⁷,
and Angel Hsu^{1,8}

* Co first-authors; corresponding author: Angel Hsu (angel.hsu@unc.edu)

¹Data-Driven EnviroLab, UNC Institute for the Environment, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill,
Chapel Hill, NC 25716

³Copernicus Institute, Utrecht University, the Netherlands

⁴Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (PBL), the Netherlands

⁵School of Humanities and Social Science, The Chinese University of Hong Kong (Shenzhen), Shenzhen,
518172, China

⁶Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK)

⁷Global Energy Systems Analysis, Technische Universität Berlin, Berlin, Germany

⁸Department of Public Policy, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Chapel Hill, NC 27516

Abstract

Cities and subnational governments are establishing their own mitigation targets and plans toward net-zero goals, yet the mitigation pathways used to assess decarbonization scenarios have been too coarse to directly evaluate urban action. Here, we develop a policy-compatible framework that links global mitigation pathways from the IMAGE integrated assessment model (IAM) under a SSP2, a middle-of-the-road socioeconomic pathway, to dynamic administrative urban units through a Kaya-based downscaling approach. We find that urban areas account for most modeled emissions reductions under both Current Policies and 2°C pathways, and they dominate the transition to net-negative emissions by the end of the century. Using an administrative boundary approach, we estimate that more than four-fifths of global emissions already occur in urban areas, with this share remaining high across regions and scenarios despite substantial and variable spatial restructuring over time. Benchmarking 3,526 subnational climate targets across the G20 reveals an uneven landscape of subnational mitigation policy ambition across countries. Compared to 2020 levels, the collective urban-pledge trajectory implies a 3.4% increase in emissions by 2030 under the 2°C benchmark, followed by a 75% decline by 2050, while under the Current Policies scenario they increase by 5.2% before declining by 40% by 2050.

Introduction

Understanding how city and subnational climate mitigation efforts contribute to global pathways towards meeting the Paris Agreement goals is a persistent challenge. Most global mitigation scenarios are generated by integrated assessment models (IAMs)¹⁻³, which represent coupled energy, land, economic, and climate systems over long time horizons and at large scales such as world regions or in some cases individual countries⁴. As a result, these scenarios provide limited guidance at the scale at which a substantial share of mitigation planning and implementation occurs. This mismatch has become increasingly consequential as cities and subnational governments have assumed a more central role in climate governance⁵⁻⁸, and are often expected to align their emission reduction targets and climate plans with global temperature goals^{9,10}.

The analytical tools to evaluate subnational governments' mitigation efforts, however, have been insufficient. Although thousands of cities and subnational governments have developed climate action plans and adopted emission reduction targets^{11–14}, existing modelling frameworks and climate scenario tools are too coarsely resolved to assess how these actions contribute to or can alter emission trajectories over time^{15,16}. IAMs provide the dominant benchmarks for global mitigation, but their broad resolution makes it difficult to gauge urban commitments within those pathways or to evaluate the cumulative contribution of city action at scale. At the same time, the empirical basis to bridge these models with urban-scale analysis has improved dramatically, with city-level socioeconomic, energy and greenhouse gas (GHG) data rapidly expanding due to the availability of high spatio-temporal data products and emerging machine learning approaches that can predict or harmonize emissions data across large numbers of subnational governments^{17,18}. These developments create new opportunities to connect global mitigation pathways to the urban scale, allowing for new insights regarding urban areas' future emission pathways and how existing subnational climate policy efforts could affect them.

One promising route is statistical downscaling of coarse-scale emission totals to finer spatial units offers^{19,20}. Scenario research has emphasized that Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) and related global scenario frameworks need to be adapted or downscaled to support both national and local analysis²¹. Previous studies have demonstrated the feasibility and importance of translating coarse-scale scenarios to finer spatial units, whether for socio-economic trajectories^{22–27}, urban land expansion²⁸, or emissions^{29–31}. Methodological choices in downscaling matter: different allocation rules and proxy variables can produce materially different local trajectories, even when they begin from the same initial scenario. Future projections and pathways are further affected by urban boundary definitions^{17,32}. For urban climate planning, these implications mean that downscaling is not necessarily a technical exercise, but a potentially normative and analytical choice that shapes how mitigation responsibility, feasibility and ambition are interpreted across jurisdictions.

In this article, we develop a novel framework that integrates downscaled global mitigation pathways from the IMAGE IAM under SSP2 with a dynamic administrative-boundary approach to derive urban policy-compatible future mitigation pathways. Our analysis focuses on territorial emission trajectories at the macro-regional level, encompassing all world regions. Specifically, we develop a Kaya-based statistical downscaling approach that applies the most appropriate socio-economic factors most relevant to urban emissions. Rather than treating urban pathways as simple proportional shares of national or regional trajectories, we show that these alternative downscaling strategies imply new insights of urban development, structural change and mitigation potential. By making underlying assumptions more explicit, we aim to advance a more transparent basis for benchmarking city mitigation targets against global pathways and for evaluating how urban climate action contributes to broader decarbonization pathways. We do this by applying a unique dataset of 3,526 subnational climate mitigation targets¹¹, enabling us, for the first time, to evaluate urban mitigation actions against urban-specific pathways to assess how subnational targets across G20 countries and regions may shape future mitigation trajectories under a policy-compatible framework.

Our results show that global mitigation is dominantly urban, and that this urban concentration remains consistent across regions and scenarios using a dynamic administrative-boundary approach. We also find

that the ambition of existing city-scale and subnational mitigation pledges is highly uneven relative to modeled urban emissions pathways, with some cities targeting reductions that are in line or even exceed Current Policies or reductions consistent with a 2°C pathway.

Results

Urban areas are central to net-negative mitigation pathways

Urban emissions trajectories closely resemble global pathways under both Current Policies and 2°C scenarios, indicating that the long-term dynamics of climate mitigation are concentrated overwhelmingly in urban areas (Figure 1). The Current Policies scenario represents policies implemented by national governments (both in rural and urban areas), while the 2°C scenario assumes cost-effective implementation of the upper limit of the Paris temperature goals. Under the Current Policies scenario, urban net emissions (excluding AFOLU and international aviation emissions) decline starting in 2020 from 25.5 (24.5 - 26.1) GtCO₂ to 15.4 (14.2 - 15.9) Gt in 2070, before increasing again to 16.2 (15.2 - 16.6) GtCO₂ by 2100. Under the 2°C pathway, urban net emissions fall to near zero by 2070 (-0.001 - 0.06) GtCO₂ and then become net negative by 2100, reaching -2.34 (-2.42 - -2.18) GtCO₂. Notably, urban areas account for the vast majority of negative emissions in this pathway, with 4.94-5.3 GtCO₂ allocated to urban areas in 2100 compared with only 0.82-1.33 GtCO₂ in rural areas (Figure 1a).

Figure 1. Comparison of Global and Downscaled urban pathways for a) net CO₂ emissions and b) gross CO₂ emissions for Current Policies and 2°C pathways.

Given the unknown future locations of negative emissions technologies, net urban emissions are compared with gross emissions. Gross emissions (Figure 1b) show a similar divergence between the Current Policies and the 2°C scenarios, although decarbonization is not driven by removals. Under Current Policies, urban gross emissions decline from 25.5 (24.5 - 26.1) GtCO₂ in 2020 to 17.0 (15.8 - 17.6) Gt in 2070 and to 16.1 (15.02 - 16.5) GtCO₂ by 2100, indicating that substantial residual urban

emissions persist throughout the century. Under the 2°C scenario, however, urban gross emissions fall much more rapidly, to 5.9 (5.5 - 6.1) GtCO₂ in 2070 and 2.9 (2.8 - 3.0) GtCO₂ by 2100.

These results highlight that ambitious urban mitigation requires both deep reductions in gross emissions and a large expansion of negative emissions. By 2100, urban areas are critical not only because they must dramatically reduce gross emissions, but also because they could account for most of the negative emissions in the 2°C pathway. In our analysis, negative emissions under the 2 °C scenario allocated to urban areas reach 4.94- 5.3 GtCO₂ in 2100, compared to the 0.82 to 1.33 GtCO₂ allocated to rural areas in the same year. However, future locations of negative emissions depend on where technologies are installed, which technologies become dominant, and how emissions are allocated in inventory accounting³³. Urban areas therefore emerge not only as the main driver of emission reductions, but could also be the primary domain in which the shift to net-negative emissions is realized. Rather than simply mirroring global pathways, our results here suggest that global decarbonization is, to a large extent, an urban process: most gross emission reductions and carbon removal required to achieve net-negative outcomes are concentrated in urban areas.

Future urbanization concentrates emissions in cities and peri-urban areas

Aggregate urban emission trajectories in our study are represented using a population- and GDP-based approach, capturing average trends across urban and rural space without prescribing specific locations of emissions or low-carbon technologies. As a result, similar national or regional trajectories may reflect different spatial dynamics, depending on whether emissions remain concentrated in established urban areas or shift toward newly urbanizing and peri-urban areas or possibly rural areas. Based on gross CO₂ emissions (excluding AFOLU and international aviation) the urban share of global emissions is estimated as 81.8% (78.8% - 83.6%) in 2020, rising to 88.2% (82.4% - 90.3%) by 2100 under the Current Policies Scenario and to 87.7% (81.9% - 89.9%) in 2100 for the 2 °C Scenario. This estimate is higher than many previously published estimates for the urban share of emissions because it reflects an administrative boundary perspective, which is intentionally more inclusive than morphology or pixel-based definitions of urban areas¹⁷.

Figure 2. Urban Share of emissions for Current Policies Scenario and 2 °C Scenario for the world and regions (see Methods for regional definitions).

At the regional level, however, the aggregate urban shares of emissions reveal different urbanization and development dynamics (Figure 2). Some regions remain consistently highly urbanized in emissions terms, with only limited change over time, such as Eastern Asia (96% in 2020 to 95% in 2100), North America (85% in 2020 to 88% in 2100) and Eastern Europe (74 % in 2020 to 76% in 2100) under the Current Policies scenario. Other regions show more pronounced increases in the urban share of emissions, including Latin America and the Caribbean (72% in 2020 to 83% in 2100); Australia, Japan and New Zealand (79% in 2020 to 88% in 2100). The largest increases occur in Africa (60% in 2020 to 84% in 2100) and Southern Asia (58% in 2020 to 98% in 2020), where ongoing urbanization and economic development shift an increasing share of emissions into urban and peri-urban administrative areas. The 2 °C scenario shows a similar regional pattern.

Importantly, relative stability in the urban share should not be interpreted as evidence of stagnant urban change. In several regions, most notably Eastern Asia, the flat trajectory (Figure 2) reflects the interaction between our downscaling approach and the dynamic reclassification of urban space (see Methods). The downscaling method allocates more emissions to administrative units with higher projected population and GDP. As some of these fast-growing administrative units fall outside urban designations, our dynamic urban identification reclassifies them as urban in later decades once their characteristics become consistent with urban centers or peri-urban areas. As a result, the near-flat urban share does not imply that Eastern Asia’s emissions are unchanged or that urbanization has stalled. Instead, this result suggests that Eastern Asia is already close to saturation in terms of urban emissions, while additional growth increasingly occurs in areas that are incorporated as urban areas over time. With fixed boundaries, results would likely show a declining urban share and a rising share of emissions in presently non-urban areas.

These results show that while urban areas remain the dominant source of emissions under both Current Policies and 2 °C scenarios, underlying urbanization dynamics are very different in various regions. In some regions, urban emissions remain persistently concentrated because urbanization is already advanced. In others the urban share rises rapidly because development and population growth bring new administrative units into the urban category. Urban emissions at both the global and regional level, with the exception of regions like Africa, Southern Asia and Middle East, tend follow the total emissions from the two scenarios very closely, maintaining a relative constant gap between the total emission and the urban emissions for the region (Figure S5)

Urban areas drive most of modeled mitigation pathways, but ambition varies across G20 cities

While downscaled urban pathways indicate substantial mitigation potential from city and subnational governments towards meeting the Paris goals, it remains an open question whether their individually pledged climate targets are ambitious enough to deliver. To address this question, we compare the collective urban-pledge trajectories of subnational governments in the G20 (i.e., Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, the European Union, Great Britain, India, Indonesia, Japan, Korea, Mexico, Turkey, the United States of America, and South Africa), where the most number of city and subnational mitigation targets are recorded¹¹ (see Methods), to the Current Policies and 2 °C pathways. This comparison allows us to assess, for the first time at this scale, whether voluntary urban commitments are aligned with the level of mitigation implied by modeled urban-specific decarbonization pathways.

Based on subnational self-reported emissions and pledge data in G20 countries^{11,34}, we find that urban areas, based on our classification (See Methods), account for 92.3% of the total emissions reduction relative to their baseline emission levels between 2020 and 2050 across. Urban emissions fall by 2,791 MtCO₂ over this period, compared with only 233 MtCO₂ in non-urban areas (Figure S6). This finding is particularly significant given the scale and near-term concentration of subnational climate commitments compared to the estimated changes for the downscaled scenarios. For the 2°C scenario we estimate an increase of 3.4% of emissions in 2030 compared to 2020, but a 75% decrease in 2050 compared to 2030. Similarly for the Current Policies scenario we estimate an increase of 5.2% by 2030 compared to 2020 and a decrease of 40% by 2050 compared to 2030. Among 2,948 quantifiable G20 subnational entities' targets with baseline years before 2020, average baseline emissions are 6.15 MtCO₂, and 2,498 of 3,526 targets (71%) aim for 2030. In terms of administrative level, 67.5% of the commitments are at the ADM3 level, indicating that most pledges are made at the city or municipality level.

Across major regions such as the EU, China (CHN), the United States (USA), Japan (JPN), and North/South Korea (KOR), a continuous decline in projected urban emissions is observed from 2020 to 2050 (Figure S7). These reductions are particularly substantial, accounting for 432 MtCO₂ reduction in China, 446 MtCO₂ in the United States, 346 MtCO₂ in Japan, and 177 MtCO₂ reduction in South Korea. In 2020, urban emissions in Japan (529 MtCO₂), United States (522 MtCO₂), and China (530 MtCO₂) are at similar base levels. However, the United States exhibits a relatively faster decline, with an average decadal reduction of approximately 148 MtCO₂, followed by China (144 MtCO₂) and Japan (115 MtCO₂).

However, the EU follows a different pattern with projected urban emissions decreasing by approximately 723 MtCO₂ between 2020 and 2030, followed by smaller reductions of 117 MtCO₂ from 2030 to 2040 and 96 MtCO₂ from 2040 to 2050. The majority of EU's urban emission reductions over the 2020 to 2050 projection period occur during the 2020 to 2030 decade, accounting for about 77.5% of the total urban emission reduction.

Figure 3 compares country-level urban emissions per capita trajectories under the Current Policies and 2 °C scenarios with the collective pledged trajectory of cities and subnational governments in each G20 country. Aggregated G20 per capita emissions for the urban-pledge pathway start at 12.7 tCO₂ per capita in 2020 and decrease to 5.0 tCO₂ per capita by 2050. Since not all urban entities have or have reported pledges, this comparison provides a suitable approach to assess the aggregate ambition of pledged urban climate action against urban-specific benchmark pathways derived from our downscaling method. By 2050, the collective urban-pledge trajectory for the G20 as a whole, as well as for the European Union, Indonesia and Japan are less ambitious compared to both 2 °C and the Current Policies scenarios. In Argentina, Australia, China, and Turkey, the collective urban-pledge pathway is more ambitious than the Current Policies scenario but less than the 2 °C scenario. The urban pledges in Brasil, Canada, Korea, India, Mexico, the United States and South Africa are more ambitious compared to both 2 °C and the Current Policies scenarios. These results underscore the need to raise ambition in many contexts and the substantial contributions that highly ambitious urban action can make to achieving global climate goals. Figure 4 provides a spatial view of the results at a global scale categorising aggregate urban pledges into four categories: more/less ambitious compared to the Current Policies/2°C national emissions per capita pathways.

Urban Trajectory by Country

Figure 3. Urban Trajectories by country in Emissions per capita.

Note: Ambition assessment is performed through the position of the urban pledge pathway compared to the Current Policies and 2 °C scenarios. Urban pledge pathways located below the 2 °C Scenario are considered less ambitious than the latter, urban-pledge pathways located above the 2 °C Scenario and below the Current Policies pathway are considered less ambitious than 2 °C Scenario but more ambitious than the Current Policies scenario, and urban-pledge pathways above both curves are considered less ambitious than both.

Figure 4. Geographic distribution of the ambition of collective urban-pledge trajectories across the G20. Note: Different clusters represent whether pledged urban action is less ambitious than current policies, between current policies and 2 °C, or more ambitious than the cost-effective 2 °C pathway.

Discussion

By linking global mitigation pathways to dynamically shifting administrative urban units, this study provides a first assessment of how city and subnational climate commitments contribute to widely used IAM climate policy scenarios. In doing so, we offer a critical benchmarking framework cities can adapt to assess their own mitigation efforts in the context of global decarbonization pathways that have long remained too coarse and abstract for urban decision-making. We show that global mitigation is overwhelmingly urban in nature, and that this urban concentration of emissions and mitigation potential is consistent across regions and scenarios using an administrative-boundary approach. When benchmarking the ambition of pledged subnational action across the G20, we find that these largely voluntary mitigation actions are highly uneven when compared to urban-specific Current Policies and 2 °C pathways. These findings and the downscaling methods developed in this paper advance a policy-compatible framework for interpreting urban climate ambition within broader decarbonization pathways, and help provide the foundation for more urban-relevant scenario analysis in future assessments, including the IPCC Special Report on Cities.

A major implication of our analysis is the centrality of urban climate action to global decarbonization pathways. In our results, urban areas account for most modeled emission reductions in both Current Policies and 2 °C pathways, indicating that the path³⁵y to deep decarbonization³⁵ is largely an urban one. However, when assessing pledged mitigation efforts by cities in the G20, which contributes around 85% of global emissions³⁶, we find uneven ambition and a gap relative to global climate goals. This insufficiency suggests a governance and implementation gap: implementation frequently lags behind target-setting due to capacity and financial constraints cities face^{37–39}, uneven multilevel governance support^{40,41}, and cities' frequent lack of agency over majority emission sources within their

administrative boundaries⁴². While we find some countries show collective urban pledges that outperform benchmark pathways, serving as potential exemplars in their mitigation targets, while others remain less ambitious than current policies.

This study is certainly not without its limitations. We built our framework around territorial CO₂ pathways, which is appropriate for linking subnational targets to IAM-derived mitigation scenarios and to governance units with formal policy authority. But territorial accounting captures only part of urban climate responsibility⁴³. Prior research comparing urban and peri-urban areas' territorial emissions compared to consumption-based emissions shows that a city's consumption-based emissions frequently exceed its territorial emissions, particularly in wealthier cities in developed countries where major emission sources (e.g., industry and electric utility) relocate outside of an urban center but a larger share of emissions is embodied in importer goods and services³². In the context of this study, benchmarking solely from a territorial-emission lens could make a city appear aligned with a deep decarbonization pathway while in reality its emissions are being displaced through consumption. Therefore, future studies should seek to explicitly integrate consumption-based accounting.⁴⁴ Second, since we primarily focus on CO₂, we are likely undercounting mitigation opportunities for cities and urban areas to reduce non-CO₂ gases, such as methane, which is a byproduct of waste and landfills. Recent observational work suggests that landfill methane emissions are substantial for urban areas, particularly in developing countries, but poorly captured in reported or modeled inventories^{45,46}. Third, our findings on net-negative urban pathways should not be interpreted as forecasts of where CO₂ removal will physically occur, but rather as an indication of where responsibility for balancing residual emissions lies within an administrative-boundary approach. This distinction is important because future CDR may depend on land availability, geological storage potential, and energy infrastructure that are frequently located outside of city centers even when policy responsibility and financing occur within an urban boundary. Fourth, our analysis considers only a cost-effective implementation of the global below 2 °C goal. Although this does not necessarily imply that cities where mitigation occurs also bear the associated costs, effort sharing approaches accounting for a fair distribution of mitigation actions could yield a different picture¹⁰. Fifth, although urban emissions can be estimated using population and GDP, additional factors could also influence these emissions^{17,18}. While this study assesses urban pledges at the aggregated country level for which population and GDP are appropriate drivers, future work can explore additional factors relevant to urban emissions. Finally, although the urban share is substantial in our analysis, actors beyond city governments such as businesses and financial institutions, play a crucial role in achieving the Paris goals, often operating within city boundaries.⁴⁷

Methods

Global and macro-region scenarios

The scenarios for macro-regions in this study were implemented in the Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment version 3.4 (IMAGE 3.4) model, which is an integrated assessment model that represents the interaction between the human and earth system and has a focus on global environmental problems such as climate change⁴⁸. The model includes 26 macro-regions across the globe, of which including some representative large countries such as the USA, China, and India. For an IAM, IMAGE has a detailed representation of economic sectors and activities.

In this study, global and macro-regional emissions were downscaled to urban areas under two distinct climate policy scenarios. Both scenarios are grounded in the SSP2 (Middle of the Road) framework, which serves as a reference socioeconomic background where social, economic, and technological trends persist along historical patterns^{2,49}. Using SSP2 as a consistent baseline allows for a direct comparison of urban emission trajectories under different policy interventions. Regarding the specific emission pathways, the Climate Policies (CP) scenario assumes that national governments only implement domestic climate, energy, and land-use measures that are already secured by law or executive orders^{3,50,51}. In contrast, the “Below 2 °C” scenario assumes a cost-effective global implementation aimed at the upper temperature limit of the Paris Agreement (with a >66% probability). This cost-effective approach prioritizes mitigation where it is least expensive, independent of equity-based effort-sharing principles or the actual source of funding for these reductions.

Downscaling using Kaya

Downscaling is the process of transforming low resolution data into finer spatial detail. In the context of IAMs, downscaling has mainly involved disaggregating macro-regional data into individual country-level estimates^{29,30}. This study advanced this process by developing a two-step approach to estimate future urban emissions. We first downscaled IMAGE-projected macro-region emissions to gridded emissions with a spatial resolution of 6 arc-minutes and then aggregated it to urban emissions using projected shifting urban boundaries over time. This approach is feasible because emerging studies have estimated diverse gridded data products from 2020 to 2100 aligned with SSP storylines for population^{22,24–26,52–54} and GDP in Power Purchasing Parity (PPP) terms^{23,25,27}. However, to our knowledge, spatially downscaled high-resolution CO₂ projections are currently unavailable, leaving a knowledge gap between high-resolution historical records and future scenarios.^{55–57}

To estimate territorial CO₂ emissions for urban areas, we downscaled IMAGE emission projections from macro-regions to urban areas by taking three key steps: 1) downscaling CO₂ emissions from the IMAGE model for the 26 macro-regions to the high-resolution grid level; 2) projecting future urbanized pixels at the grid level; 3) consolidating the gridded CO₂ emissions data for urban areas.

The emissions downscaling was achieved by using a Kaya downscaling approach. The Kaya approach assumes that population and GDP are the primary drivers of territorial CO₂ emissions, as described by the Kaya identity⁵⁸ (Eq. 1). We applied a method based on van Vuuren²⁹, which uses the Kaya identity to downscale CO₂ emissions from macro-regional scenario projections to the country level. In this study, we advanced this approach by proceeding to grid-cell level, which enabled aggregation to urban areas based on spatially downscaled high-resolution gridded emissions (Eq. 2). First, population, GDP (PPP) per capita, and CO₂ intensity (CO₂ per unit of GDP in PPP) were calculated for each grid cell on gridded population^{22,52} and GDP (PPP)²³ projections. For this purpose, we selected projections consistent with the SSP2 scenario and compiled a dataset covering the period 2020 to 2100 at ten-year intervals. Second, CO₂ intensity per grid cell was calculated for the last available historical year from CEDS/CMIP^{7,59,60}, which further excludes AFOLU, waste, aviation, and shipping sectors because of lack of representation in urban areas. In addition to net CO₂ emissions, we calculated gross emissions by excluding negative emissions from Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) in the energy supply and industry sectors. The CO₂ intensity of each grid cell was estimated under the assumption that it converges toward the value of its corresponding macro-region (see Eq. 3). While this convergence reaches completion in 2150, the values for 2100

represent a state of partial convergence. To this end, it was assumed that emissions and GDP (PPP) values would remain constant between 2100 and 2150. Third, the Kaya identity is applied to estimate annual CO₂ emissions for each grid cell, resulting in a dataset with a spatial resolution of 6 arc-minutes. To ensure consistency with the IAM scenarios, CO₂ emissions were harmonized using a scaling factor defined as the ratio between the sum of gridded emissions per year for each region and the corresponding maro-regional emissions from the model.

$$CO2 = POP * (GDP/POP) * (CO2/GDP) \quad (1)$$

$$CO2_{t,x,y} = POP_{t,x,y} \times (GDP^{PPP}_{t,x,y}/POP_{t,x,y}) \times (CO2_{t,x,y}/GDP^{PPP}_{t,x,y}) \times HF_{t,R} \quad (2)$$

$$\left(\frac{CO2}{GDP^{PPP}}\right)_{t,x,y} = \left(\frac{CO2}{GDP^{PPP}}\right)_{t0,x,y} + \frac{T-t}{T-t0} \times \left(\left(\frac{CO2}{GDP^{PPP}}\right)_{T,x,y} - \left(\frac{CO2}{GDP^{PPP}}\right)_{t0,x,y} \right) \quad (3)$$

where *CO2* is Carbon dioxide emissions; *POP* is Population; *GDP* is Gross Domestic Product; *PPP* is Power Purchasing Parity; *HF* is Harmonisation factor; *t* is time; *t0* is last available historical year, *T* is convergence year, *R* is model region; *x,y* is longitude, latitude (coordinates), respectively.

Projecting urbanization trends

To account for rising urbanization over time, we developed a dynamic administrative-boundary approach that updates the classification of administrative entities as urban or rural across selected time steps. To our knowledge, this is the first explicit future-scenario framework to incorporate dynamically changing administrative boundaries in urban mitigation pathways. Our method builds on the initial classification proposed by¹⁷, which categorizes administrative entities in the GADM 4.1 dataset as urban (urban center + peri-urban) or rural using indicators that capture human settlement activities, and includes population density, GDP per capita, electricity consumption, and built-up proportion and trend over a 40-year period. Using the classification results together with a similar set of predictors (i.e., population⁶¹, GDP²³ and built-up area⁶¹) extracted from gridded databases compatible with SSP2 pathways, we trained and validated a binary classification machine learning model (XGBoost)⁶² to predict whether each administrative entity should be classified as urban or rural. For each year, the model estimates the probability that an administrative entity should be classified as urban. We then use these predictions to assign entities to urban or rural categories under a range of probability thresholds (50% to 90%) to represent different urbanization conditions through 2100. For example, under the 70% threshold, entities with a predicted probability of at least 0.7 probability or higher are classified as urban.

The machine learning model (XGBoost) achieved 97.0% accuracy, 96.1% precision (proportion of predicted target items that are actually target items), and 94.5% recall (proportion of actual target items that are correctly predicted as target items), indicating strong performance in distinguishing urban from rural areas while maintaining low rates of false positives and false negatives. Figure S4 presents how much each input variable contributes to the predictions (feature importance), showing that built-up proportion, population density, and GDP per capita are the three most important predictors. As a final adjustment, we imposed a no-regression rule under which entities classified as urban would not revert to rural status in later years, aligning with the continuous persistence of built-up land, which typically

remains even where population or economic productivity declines. In other words, once an entity was classified as urban, it remained urban in all subsequent years. A summary of the classification results are available in Table S1.

Based on the assumption of a 70% probability threshold, our results indicate that by 2050, 78.8% or 7.24 billion people globally will fall within urban administrative boundaries by 2050, rising to 91.5% or 8.3 billion people by 2100. These shares are similar to the latest United Nations World Urbanization Prospects projection⁶³ that estimates an 82.9% urban (Cities + Towns) population share in 2050. Under the SSP2 baseline scenario, Asia and Latin America account for most of the increase in urbanized areas until 2060, after which Africa will see the majority of the increase towards 2100. Europe and North America see smaller increases due to their already high urbanization levels in 2020 (Figure 5).

a)

Urban-Rural Classification (70%) 2050

b)

Urban-Rural Classification (70%) 2100

Figure 5. Urban-Rural classification estimates at the 70% probability for a) 2050 and b) 2100.

Emissions levels based on city reduction targets

To benchmark and evaluate city-level mitigation targets, we implemented a two-step process to compare subnational governments' climate commitments to the downscaled scenarios. We utilized the ClimActor dataset, which contains self-reported emissions data and mitigation commitments from subnational governments (i.e., cities, states, and regions) reported to public disclosure platforms like CDP, the Global Covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy, and other sources¹¹. These commitments specify target years and percentage emission reductions relative to historical baseline, enabling the modeling of emission trajectories for each subnational entity. Each entity is represented by one of the Global Administrative Areas (GADM)⁶⁴ geometries, enabling the identification of urban areas that have pledged a quantifiable climate mitigation target.

The emission trajectories for subnational entities were constructed based on the ClimActor's dataset. First, emissions in the target year were computed based on the entities' target reductions relative to the baseline emissions. Linear interpolation was then applied to connect base-year emissions, intermediate self-reported emissions, and target-year emissions. This approach resulted in emissions projections for each entity, for the years 2020, 2030, 2040, and 2050. Once an entity reaches its target year, emissions are assumed to remain constant at that level afterwards.

To estimate emissions trajectories for urban entities, we explicitly distinguished between urban and non-urban administrative areas. This approach was also used for the downscaled pathways based on the Kaya identity. The urban classification is determined by the proportion of urban area within each entity, based on an urban-rural layer derived from the XGBoost model described above. While the underlying layer is pixel based, the final urban share is assigned at the level of administrative boundaries. Specifically, an ADM entity is classified as urban if at least 95% of its pixels are identified as urban (Figure S8). In addition, major cities that are defined at the ADM1 level are retained to represent key metropolitan areas (e.g., Beijing, Berlin, etc.).

To prevent double counting, overlapping ADM entities were excluded and to ensure global spatial coverage. After classifying the urban and rural ADMs, total emissions were aggregated across the type of ADM entities at the country (ISO) level for 2020, 2030, 2040, and 2050. In addition, to ensure comparability between the projected emission trajectories and the Kaya-based emission prediction, we harmonize population data from the 2UP dataset.⁶⁵ This allows us to compute per capita emissions (i.e., total emissions divided by population) and evaluate whether the urban emission pathways for each country are consistent with either current policies scenarios or a 2 °C pathway.

Code Availability

The code for the Kaya downscaling approach can be found at https://github.com/imagepbl/downscaling/tree/main/Kaya_downscaling

Data Availability

Datasets developed for this paper are available on the Data-Driven EnviroLab's Dataverse page.³⁴ (<https://doi.org/10.15139/S3/THMDLV>)

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Funding

The project was supported by the IKEA Foundation (RG-2306-02289). Mark Roelfsema was also supported by HORIZON EUROPE Framework Programme: [grant number 101137625: ACHIEVE].

References

1. van Vuuren, D. P. *et al.* The use of scenarios as the basis for combined assessment of climate change mitigation and adaptation. *Glob. Environ. Change* **21**, 575–591 (2011).
2. Riahi, K. *et al.* The Shared Socioeconomic Pathways and their energy, land use, and greenhouse gas emissions implications: An overview. *Glob. Environ. Change* **42**, 153–168 (2017).
3. Roelfsema, M. *et al.* Developing scenarios in the context of the Paris Agreement and application in the integrated assessment model IMAGE: A framework for bridging the policy-modelling divide. *Environ. Sci. Policy* **135**, 104–116 (2022).
4. Calvin, K. *et al.* GCAM v5. 1: representing the linkages between energy, water, land, climate, and economic systems. *Geosci. Model Dev.* **12**, 677–698 (2019).
5. Bulkeley, H. & Betsill, M. Rethinking Sustainable Cities: Multilevel Governance and the ‘Urban’ Politics of Climate Change. *Environ. Polit.* **14**, 42–63 (2005).
6. Bulkeley, H. & Betsill, M. M. Revisiting the urban politics of climate change. *Environ. Polit.* **22**, 136–154 (2013).
7. Hsu, A. *et al.* A research roadmap for quantifying non-state and subnational climate mitigation action. *Nat. Clim. Change* **9**, 11–17 (2019).
8. Song, K., Farr, K. B. & Hsu, A. Assessing subnational climate action in G20 cities and regions: Progress and ambition. *One Earth* **0**, (2024).

9. Lwasa, S. *et al.* Urban systems and other settlements. in *Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change* (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Geneva, Switzerland, 2022).
10. Robiou du Pont, Y., Manya, D., Song, K., Haarstad, H. & Hsu, A. From countries to cities: assessing climate ambition with a multi-level fair-share allocation framework. Preprint at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19354696> (2026).
11. Manya, D., Farr, K. B., Brown, E., Martin, A. & Hsu, A. ClimActor 2.0: A spatialized database of subnational climate pledges and emissions data. <https://eartharxiv.org/repository/view/10382/> (2025).
12. Sharifi, A., Seto, K. C. & Aboagye, P. D. The literature landscape on cities and climate change. *Urban Clim.* **66**, 102849 (2026).
13. Rivas, S., Urraca, R., Palermo, V. & Bertoldi, P. Covenant of Mayors 2020: Drivers and barriers for monitoring climate action plans. *J. Clean. Prod.* **332**, 130029 (2022).
14. Croci, E., Lucchitta, B., Janssens-Maenhout, G., Martelli, S. & Molteni, T. Urban CO₂ mitigation strategies under the Covenant of Mayors: An assessment of 124 European cities. *J. Clean. Prod.* **169**, 161–177 (2017).
15. Seto K. C *et al.* Human settlements, infrastructure, and spatial planning. in *Climate Change 2014: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (ed. Edenhofer R. Pichs-Madruga, Y. Sokona, E. Farahani, S. Kadner, K. Seyboth, A. Adler, I. Baum, S. Brunner, P. Eickemeier, B. Kriemann, J. Savolainen, S. Schlömer, C. von Stechow, T. Zwickel and J.C. Minx (eds.), O.) (Cambridge University Press, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 2014).
16. Lwasa, S. *et al.* Urban systems and other settlements. in *Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change* (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Geneva, Switzerland, 2022).

17. Yu, Y., Wang, X., Many, D. & Hsu, A. Machine learning estimates for G20 subnational urban GHG emissions from 2000–2020. *Sci. Data* **13**, 487 (2026).
18. Hsu, A., Wang, X., Tan, J., Toh, W. & Goyal, N. Predicting European cities' climate mitigation performance using machine learning. *Nat. Commun.* **13**, 7487 (2022).
19. IPCC. *IPCC Workshop on the Use of Scenarios in the Sixth Assessment Report and Subsequent Assessments*.
https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2023/07/IPCC_2023_Workshop_Report_Scenarios.pdf
(2023).
20. van Vuuren, D. P., Smith, S. J. & Riahi, K. Downscaling socioeconomic and emissions scenarios for global environmental change research: a review. *WIREs Clim. Change* **1**, 393–404 (2010).
21. Wang, H. *et al.* Bridging China's Climate Targets and Mitigation Capacity through Sectoral Policy Implementation. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5c11232> (2026)
[doi:10.1021/acs.est.5c11232](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5c11232).
22. Huistee, J., van Bommel, B., Bouwman, A., & van Rijn, F. *Towards an Urban Review. Modelling Future Urban Growth with 2UP. Background Report*.
https://www.pbl.nl/uploads/default/downloads/pbl-2018-Towards-an-urban-preview_3255.pdf
(2018).
23. Murakami, D., Yoshida, T. & Yamagata, Y. Gridded GDP Projections Compatible With the Five SSPs (Shared Socioeconomic Pathways). *Front. Built Environ.* **7**, (2021).
24. Zhuang, H. *et al.* Mapping high-resolution global gridded population distribution from 1870 to 2100. *Sci. Total Environ.* **955**, 176867 (2024).

25. Murakami, D. & Yamagata, Y. Estimation of Gridded Population and GDP Scenarios with Spatially Explicit Statistical Downscaling. *Sustainability* **11**, (2019).
26. Wang, X., Meng, X. & Long, Y. Projecting 1 km-grid population distributions from 2020 to 2100 globally under shared socioeconomic pathways. *Sci. Data* **9**, 563 (2022).
27. Wang, T. & Sun, F. Global gridded GDP data set consistent with the shared socioeconomic pathways. *Sci. Data* **9**, 221 (2022).
28. Gao, J. & Pesaresi, M. Downscaling SSP-consistent global spatial urban land projections from 1/8-degree to 1-km resolution 2000–2100. *Sci. Data* **8**, 281 (2021).
29. van Vuuren, D. P., Lucas, P. L. & Hilderink, H. Downscaling drivers of global environmental change: Enabling use of global SRES scenarios at the national and grid levels. *Glob. Environ. Change* **17**, 114–130 (2007).
30. Gidden, M. J. *et al.* Global emissions pathways under different socioeconomic scenarios for use in CMIP6: a dataset of harmonized emissions trajectories through the end of the century. *Geosci. Model Dev.* **12**, 1443–1475 (2019).
31. Sferra, F., van Ruijven, B. & Riahi, K. Downscaling IAMs results to the country level – a new algorithm. <https://iiasa.dev.local/> (2021).
32. Yu, Y., Manya, D. & Hsu, A. Aligning emissions with decisionmaking: estimating urban contributions to global carbon dioxide emissions. <https://eartharxiv.org/repository/view/9161/> (2025).
33. Negative emission technologies. in *Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage* 1–13 (Academic Press, 2019). doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-816229-3.00001-6.

34. Manya-Gutierrez, D., Roelfsema, M., Zhang, Y., Yu, Y. & Hsu, A. Data for: Downscaling Urban Paper - Data-Driven EnviroLab Dataverse.
35. Bataille, C., Waisman, H., Colombier, M., Segafredo, L. & Williams, J. The Deep Decarbonization Pathways Project (DDPP): insights and emerging issues. *Clim. Policy* **16**, S1–S6 (2016).
36. UNEP. *Emissions Gap Report 2025: Off Target - Continued Collective Inaction Puts Global Temperature Goal at Risk*. <https://www.unep.org/resources/emissions-gap-report-2025> (2025).
37. Diezmartínez, C. V. & Short Gianotti, A. G. Municipal finance shapes urban climate action and justice. *Nat. Clim. Change* **14**, 247–252 (2024).
38. Hadfield, P. & Cook, N. Financing the Low-Carbon City: Can Local Government Leverage Public Finance to Facilitate Equitable Decarbonisation? *Urban Policy Res.* **37**, 13–29 (2019).
39. Todeschi, V., Hernandez-Moral, G., Clementi, E., Bertoldi, P. & Melica, G. Financing climate change mitigation actions in cities: insights from the Covenant of Mayors initiative. *Sustain. Cities Soc.* **136**, 107097 (2026).
40. Fuhr, H., Hickmann, T. & Kern, K. The role of cities in multi-level climate governance: local climate policies and the 1.5 °C target. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* **30**, 1–6 (2018).
41. Lee, T. & Koski, C. Multilevel governance and urban climate change mitigation. *Environ. Plan. C Gov. Policy* **33**, 1501–1517 (2015).
42. Millard-Ball, A. The Limits to Planning: Causal Impacts of City Climate Action Plans. *J. Plan. Educ. Res.* **33**, 5–19 (2013).
43. Moran, D. *et al.* Carbon footprints of 13 000 cities. *Environ. Res. Lett.* **13**, 064041 (2018).

44. Gurney, K. R. *et al.* Greenhouse gas emissions from global cities under SSP/RCP scenarios, 1990 to 2100. *Glob. Environ. Change* **73**, 102478 (2022).
45. Plant, G. *et al.* Large Fugitive Methane Emissions From Urban Centers Along the U.S. East Coast. *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **46**, 8500–8507 (2019).
46. Hopkins, F. M. *et al.* Mitigation of methane emissions in cities: How new measurements and partnerships can contribute to emissions reduction strategies. *Earths Future* **4**, 408–425 (2016).
47. Kuramochi, T. *et al.* Beyond national climate action: the impact of region, city, and business commitments on global greenhouse gas emissions. *Clim. Policy* **20**, 275–291 (2020).
48. Stehfest, E. *et al.* *Integrated Assessment of Global Environmental Change with Model Description and Policy Applications IMAGE 3.0*. <https://www.pbl.nl/en/publications/integrated-assessment-of-global-environmental-change-with-image-30-model-description-and-policy-applications> (2014).
49. Fricko, O. *et al.* The marker quantification of the Shared Socioeconomic Pathway 2: A middle-of-the-road scenario for the 21st century. *Glob. Environ. Change* **42**, 251–267 (2017).
50. Dafnomilis, I., den Elzen, M. & van Vuuren, D. Paris targets within reach by aligning, broadening and strengthening net-zero pledges. *Commun. Earth Environ.* **5**, 1–10 (2024).
51. PBL. *Holding the Course in a Shifting World. Annual Net-Zero Report 2025*. https://88358077-e56b-453b-a945-59016389d92d.filesusr.com/ugd/a47a40_02969589069d4c418aa7236fc55ae9eb.pdf (2025).
52. van Bommel, B. *TowardsAnUrbanPreview 2UP 2024 GHSL2014 M1 M3 Total Population 2010-2100 WGS84*. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17412102> (2025).

53. HORIZON-COMPASS. GitHub - HORIZON-COMPASS/Exposure-and-vulnerability-modelling at D3_1_1_revised. *GitHub* https://github.com/HORIZON-COMPASS/Exposure-and-vulnerability-modelling/tree/D3_1_1_revised.
54. Southampton, W., University of. *WorldPop Book of Methods*.
55. Crippa, M. *et al.* Global anthropogenic emissions in urban areas: patterns, trends, and challenges. *Environ. Res. Lett.* **16**, 074033 (2021).
56. Crippa, M. *et al.* EDGAR -Emissions urban areas. (2024).
57. Hoesly, R. *et al.* CEDS v_2025_04_18 Gridded Emissions Data 0.5 degree. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15127477> (2025) doi:10.5281/zenodo.15127477.
58. Kaya, Y., Yokobori, K. & Tokyo Conference on "Global Environment, E., and Economic Development". *Environment, Energy, and Economy : Strategies for Sustainability*. (United Nations University Press, Tokyo, 1997).
59. CEDS. CEDS v_2024_04_01 Release Emission Data. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10904360> (2025).
60. McDuffie, E. E. *et al.* A global anthropogenic emission inventory of atmospheric pollutants from sector- and fuel-specific sources (1970–2017): an application of the Community Emissions Data System (CEDS). *Earth Syst. Sci. Data* **12**, 3413–3442 (2020).
61. Zhao, Q., Meng, Q., Gao, L. & Zhu, M. FU3D: the first global projections of future urban three-dimensional (3D) expansion for the 21st century under shared socioeconomic pathways. *Sci. Data* **12**, 1555 (2025).

62. Chen, T. & Guestrin, C. XGBoost: A Scalable Tree Boosting System. in *Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* 785–794 (ACM, San Francisco California USA, 2016). doi:10.1145/2939672.2939785.
63. United Nations. *World Urbanization Prospects 2025: Summary of Results*.
<https://desapublications.un.org/publications/world-urbanization-prospects-2025-summary-results>
(2025).
64. GADM. GADM maps and data. (2025).
65. Koomen, E. *et al.* An integrated global model of local urban development and population change. *Comput. Environ. Urban Syst.* **100**, 101935 (2023).

Supplementary Information

Cities and urban areas are central to global decarbonization pathways

The pattern scaling approach is used as a sensitivity to the Kaya downscaling approach. is a variant of the Kaya approach (Luderer et al., manuscript submitted). The main difference with the first approach is that it further downscales macro-regional emissions into sectoral levels, and only uses one socio-economic factor for the sectoral downscaling. The sectors include energy supply, industry, transport, buildings, land use, and waste. To calculate sectoral CO₂ emissions at the grid level, country CO₂ emissions were downscaled using either population or GDP (PPP) (see Eq. 4). It was assumed that population was the most important driver for emissions in the building sectors, while this was GDP (PPP) for the transport, energy and industry sectors.

$$CO2_{t,,s,x,y} = \underline{CO2_{t0,,s,x,y}} \times \frac{\overline{CO2_{t,,s,x,y}}}{\overline{CO2_{t0,R,s}}} \times \frac{P_{t,x,y}/P_{t0,x,y}}{P_{t,R}/P_{t0,R}} \times HF_{t,R,s} \quad (4)$$

where $CO2$ is Carbon dioxide; P is Population or GDP (PPP); HF is Harmonisation factor; t is time; $t0$ is last available historical year; R is model region; s is sector; x,y is longitude, latitude (coordinates), respectively.

IMAGE downscaling results

The downscaling of model CO₂ emissions (excl. AFOLU and aviation) was based on population and GDP (PPP) data with resolution 0.5 arc minutes and CO₂ data for the year 2020 with a resolution of 6 arc minutes. Therefore, the downscaled emissions had a resolution of 6 arc minutes. Figure S1 shows the histogram and geographical map of CO₂ emissions for the years 2020 and 2050 in the Current Policies and 'Below 2 °C' scenarios. In addition, Figure S2, shows the CO₂ emissions for the grid cell per macro-region, for the years 2020 and 2050 for the Current Policies and 'Below 2 °C' scenarios.

CO2 Emissions Projections (2015–2050)

Figure S1: gross and net emissions (excl. AFOLU and aviation) in the Current Policies and Below 2 °C scenario from the IMAGE model. Region definitions at: https://models.pbl.nl/image/Region_classification_map

Histogram of CO2 emissions for scenario ELV-SSP2-CP and year 2020

Histogram of CO2 emissions for scenario ELV-SSP2-CP and year 2050

Histogram of CO2 emissions for scenario ELV-SSP2-1150F and year 2020

Histogram of CO2 emissions for scenario ELV-SSP2-1150F and year 2050

Figure S2: Histograms and maps of CO₂ emissions (excl AFOLU and aviation) for the years 2020 and 2050, and Current Policies scenario (ELV-CP-SSP2) and ‘Below 2 °C’ scenario (ELV-SSP2-1150F)

Emissions_CO2_Excl_shipping_aviation_AFOLU per grid cell per model region for scenario ELV-SSP2-CP

Emissions_CO2_Excl_shipping_aviation_AFOLU per grid cell per model region for scenario ELV-SSP2-1150F

Figure S3: Downscaled urban CO₂ emissions (excl. AFOLU and aviation) range for the grid cells at 6 minutes resolution for each macro-region (x-axis) in the IMAGE model; Top: Current Policies scenario (ELV-CP-SSP2) Bottom: ‘Below 2 °C’ scenario (ELV-SSP2-1150F)

Figure S4 - Urban Rural Classification Model’s Feature Importance Plot.

Classification	Year	Population	GDP PPP (2005 USD)	Global Population %	Total GDP %
Rural Area	2020	2588287086	1.95E+13	33.93%	19.91%
Urban Area	2020	5040756314	7.84E+13	66.07%	80.09%
Rural Area	2030	2549448599	2.61E+13	30.76%	18.78%
Urban Area	2030	5739219405	1.13E+14	69.24%	81.22%
Rural Area	2040	2217866594	3.02E+13	25.15%	16.73%
Urban Area	2040	6600953645	1.50E+14	74.85%	83.27%
Rural Area	2050	1955661530	3.52E+13	21.25%	15.68%
Urban Area	2050	7247785602	1.89E+14	78.75%	84.32%
Rural Area	2060	1651679420	4.10E+13	17.53%	15.04%
Urban Area	2060	7768681898	2.32E+14	82.47%	84.96%
Rural Area	2070	1337293148	4.67E+13	14.09%	14.28%
Urban Area	2070	8154111158	2.81E+14	85.91%	85.72%
Rural Area	2080	1056630242	5.24E+13	11.19%	13.52%
Urban Area	2080	8384398738	3.35E+14	88.81%	86.48%
Rural Area	2090	865330784	6.00E+13	9.32%	13.23%
Urban Area	2090	8422905601	3.93E+14	90.68%	86.77%
Rural Area	2100	764990832	6.97E+13	8.44%	13.29%
Urban Area	2100	8303414455	4.55E+14	91.56%	86.71%

Table S1. Summary of main variables for urban-rural classification.

Figure S5. Total urban emissions for Current Policies Scenario (IMAGE_ELV-SSP2-CP-D01) and 2 °C Scenario (IMAGE_ELV-SSP2-1150F) for the world and each IPCC region.

Figure S6. Urban v.s. Non-urban shares of projected emissions across G20 countries

Figure S7. Urban v.s. Non-urban emission trajectories across G20 countries

Figure S8. Density of urban share by ADM Level with the threshold of 95%